

Dr Sara Mitić,
Docent,
Pravni fakultet, Univerzitet u Nišu,
Republika Srbija

UDK: 342.726-053.2(497.11)(091)

UDK: 341.231.14-053.2

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17812883

ZAŠTITA PRAVA DETETA U SRBIJI – ISTORIJSKI PREGLED

Zaštita dece predstavlja jedan od najpouzdanijih pokazatelja civilizacijskog dometa jednog društva i stepena razvijenosti njegovih pravnih institucija. Ovaj rad ima za cilj da prikaže istorijsku evoluciju mehanizama zaštite prava deteta na prostoru Srbije, sagledanu kroz različite pravne i političke epohe. U tom kontekstu biće analizirani relevantni izvori srednjovekovne Srbije koji se odnose na položaj i zaštitu najmlađih. Posebna pažnja biće posvećena normativnim rešenjima Kneževine i Kraljevine Srbije, sa fokusom na razvoj institucionalnih formi zaštite i njihov postepeni prelaz iz lokalnih i dobrotvornih okvira u formalizovani pravni sistem. Centralni deo rada obuhvata analizu pravnog uređenja u Kraljevini Srba, Hrvata i Slovenaca, kao i u Kraljevini Jugoslaviji, u kojima se pojavljuju prvi oblici sistematizovane i državno organizovane brige o deci. Istorijski pregled koji rad pruža ima za cilj da osvetli kontinuitet, transformacije i specifičnosti mehanizama zaštite dece, te ukaže na značaj ovih procesa za formiranje savremenog shvatanja i normativnog okvira zaštite prava deteta u Srbiji.

Ključne reči: dete, zaštita, prava deteta, pravna zaštita, istorijski razvoj.

Sara Mitić, LL.D.,
Assistant Professor,
Faculty of Law, University of Niš,
Republic of Serbia

PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD IN SERBIA: A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW

Child protection is one of the most reliable indicators of the civilizational attainments of a society and the level of development of its legal institutions. This paper aims to present the historical evolution of mechanisms for the protection of the rights of the child in Serbia, examined through different legal and political epochs. In this context, the paper analyzes the relevant Serbian medieval sources concerning the position and protection of minors. Special attention is given to the normative solutions envisaged in the Principality of Serbia and the Kingdom of Serbia, focusing on the development of institutional forms of protection and their gradual transition from local and charitable frameworks into a formalized legal system. The central part of the paper includes the analysis of the legal framework in the Kingdom of the Serbs, Croats and Slovenes, and the legal framework in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, where the first forms of systematized and state-organized child protection emerged. This historical overview seeks to highlight the continuity, transformations, and specific characteristics of child-protection mechanisms and to emphasize their significance for the development of the new conceptions and the contemporary normative framework for the protection of the rights of the child in Serbia.

Keywords: child, protection, children's rights, legal protection, historical development.